

Investigation on iodine partition coefficient in quaternary liquid at 301.15 K

Man Singh

Chemistry Research Laboratory, Deshbandhu College, University of Delhi, New Delhi-110 019, India

E-mail : mansingh50@hotmail.com Fax : 91-011-6417959

Manuscript received 6 March 2000, revised 22 February 2001, accepted 7 March 2001

I₂ partition in two-phase liquids constituted by CS₂ + H₂O, CCl₄ + H₂O and C₂H₂Cl₄ + H₂O solvents in presence of urea or thiourea in water phase has been studied at 301.15 K. The water and organic solvent separate phases are formed due to their electronic arrangement. I₂ partition in them is obtained by Flory-Huggins equation. The I₂ partition is subjected to the continuous and uniform thermodynamic approach of the liquids. Transition state theory and pairwise interaction parameters are considered for interpretation. Unequal chemical potential and dipole moment of water and organic solvent cause energy gradient and competition among their molecules to push I₂ towards equilibrium state. The prominent energy gradient at interfacial double layer seems to facilitate I₂ across to counter phases. Urea or thiourea addition to water phase furnishes vital information on I₂ distribution without external force. For self-controlled I₂ partition with a vector flow in liquid phases various thermodynamic equations are used.

I₂ is widely used in chemistry and medicine. Out of its 30 recognized isotopes, isotope of 127 atomic number is stable. An artificial isotope of atomic number of 132 with half-life of 8 days is applied for thyroid treatment. Occasionally¹ salts or solvents² used as its vehicle are named as 'iodated'. Recently WHO, UNICEF and ICCIDD (International Council for Control of Iodine Deficiency Disorders) have recommended the term 'iodized' for iodized common salts, as 100 µg of KI + 10 g of NaCl, and this is used as common source for iodine intake. Its other combinations, notably I₂ with KI in alcohol and betadine and triadine, gel of I₂ + PVP (polyvinylpyrrolidone) are used for curing injuries. About 10 mg of I₂ is found in our body and 70–80% of it is covalently bound with thyroid gland to controls its function. In body, I₂ intake from milk, eggs and seafood food occurs as I⁻ (iodide) to synthesize tetraiodothyronine (thyroxin hormone) in thyroid gland, and body needs about 100–200 µg of I₂ a day.

Urea³ and thiourea affect I₂ partition behaviour in aqueous solution^{4,5}, as I₂ with urea determines fat and oils saturation and prevents its escape from solution. This mechanism⁶ is widely used for protein denaturation^{7,8} and separation of kerosene and paraffin by adsorption⁶. Urea molecules by wrapping the straight-chain hydrocarbons (C = 7) form a adducts of about 0.8–1.2 nm diameter channels at crystallization and round hydrocarbon molecules in the form of hexagonal spiral accommodating straight-chain molecules with them. This mechanism is activated by methanol + acetone for kerosene separation. Hydrocarbon + urea³ complexes crystallize out and on washing with paraffin, hot water releases paraffin from the complex.

Urea^{9,10} as a hydrotropic agent with alkyl sulfonates, appears to maintain the cloud point and increases the efficiency of heavy-duty detergents. Interestingly urea electrode is devised putting urea molecules in a gel; from gel, urea diffuses to gel enzyme and the enzyme in combine catalyses urea hydrolysis to form NH₄⁺ and the latter is diffused to surface of electrode to generate potential. I₂ partition to water seems to depend on water structure; urea and thiourea actively break polymeric water to monomeric one. In our work, quaternary liquids are designed to study the I₂ partition in distinguished liquid phases, because I₂ mechanism as radiomedicine to diagnose diseases is a function of its partition and electronic transitions, and this state of I₂ induces informatory interactions^{8,11}. Further, I₂ partition in quaternary liquid phases may facilitate the recovery and purification of bioproducts of biotechnological interests; *k* is fundamental help for designing such a solution¹².

Phase intercross transport : Chemical transfer across the liquid phases through interdiction potential⁹ is useful, as evaporation of sweat with heat removal from body for survival in hot climate. Ionic transport from inside a cell to outside generates vital nerve conduction. Lower density phase rises to top in gravitational field. Free energy transfer between phases and equality at equilibrium can evaluate I₂ activity at saturated condition in solvents, and is instructive for dialysis membranes and molecular diffusion in concentration gradient of poorly mixed solvent¹³. I₂ mobility due to energy gradient brings H₂O and organic solvents (OS) together. Probably OS involves collision activation, pushing I₂ intercross from OS to water. Such interaction

may modify their activities and free energies influencing industrial extractions to remove the undesirable constituents and harmful ingredients of petroleum oils and industrial liquids. For such processes, it is essential to know how much solvent and how many treatments are needed for separation

Mathematical correlation : Energetics is used for I_2 partition to A and B solvents, with partial free energies G_A and G_B as eqns. (1) and (2). G_A^0 , G_B^0 , a_A and a_B are standard free energies and activities of I_2 in A and B.

$$G_A = G_A^0 + RT \ln a_A \quad (1)$$

$$G_B = G_B^0 + RT \ln a_B \quad (2)$$

where G_A , G_B , a_A and a_B are free energies and activities of I_2 in A and B solvent. At equilibrium, eqns. (1) and (2) are rearranged to eqn. (3) by putting $G_A = G_B$,

$$-(G_A^0 - G_B^0) = -\Delta G^0 = RT \ln \frac{a_B}{a_A} \quad (3)$$

Further, at equilibrium, term $(G_A^0 - G_B^0)/RT$ is a constant. For dilution, activities ratio becomes as eqn. (4),

$$\frac{a_B}{a_A} = \frac{c_B}{c_A}, \text{ and } \frac{c_B}{c_A} = k(\text{partition coefficient}) \quad (4)$$

c_B and c_A are I_2 concentrations, and k helps in extraction, analysis, equilibrium constant determination and substance separation from aqueous solutions with ether, $CHCl_3$, CCl_4 and C_6H_6 . Extracted solute weight could be calculated from eqn. (5),

$$W_n = W \left(\frac{k V_1}{k V_1 + V_2} \right)^n \quad (5)$$

where W_n is the unextracted solute, W the total weight, V_1 the solution volume, V_2 the second solvent and n is the number of extraction. k is very useful to calculate the extracted solute as eqn. (6),

$$W - W_n = W \left[1 - \left(\frac{k V_1}{k V_1 + V_2} \right)^n \right] \quad (6)$$

Similarly, the extraction efficiency in V_2 with k could be measured as eqn. (7),

$$E\% = 100 \left[\frac{W V_1}{W V_1 + W V_2} \right] \quad (7)$$

The collisions (since I_2 diffuses across phases in its molecular form and is large sized molecule like a spherical ball, here all molecules as H_2O , CCl_4 , CS_2 and $C_2H_2Cl_4$ retain their molecular identity and do not dissociate because of their almost negligible polarity, and hence application of collision equation is valid) occurring between I_2 and I_2 , I_2 and H_2O , and I_2-I_2 and I_2-H_2O seem to monitor I_2 partition and encounters in solvent cage as eqns. (8) and (9),

$$Z_{I_2-I_2} = \pi \sigma^2 I_2 - I_2 \sqrt{\frac{8kT}{\nu\mu}} N^2 I_2 - I_2 \quad (8)$$

$$Z_{I_2-H_2O} = \pi \sigma^2 I_2 - H_2O \sqrt{\frac{8kT}{\pi\mu}} N_{I_2} - N_{H_2O} \quad (9)$$

where $Z_{I_2-I_2}$ and $Z_{I_2-H_2O}$ are collisions, $\sigma_{I_2-I_2}^2$ and $(\sigma_{I_2-H_2O}^2)$ are average diameter, K Boltzmann constant, T temperature, μ reduced mass of colliding molecules and $N_{I_2-I_2}^2$ and $N_{I_2-H_2O}^2$ are colliding molecules of iodine and iodine, iodine and water. These collisions cause transitions in water and I_2 and initiate interactions between dipole moment of water and induced dipole moment of I_2 ; for this state k is rationalized as eqn. (10),

$$k = \left(\frac{kT}{h} \right) K^*, \text{ but } K^* = \exp \left(\frac{\Delta G^*}{RT} \right) \quad (10)$$

where K^* (transition constant), ΔG^* (free energy at transition state) and R (gas constant) are functions of transition state and are associated to ΔS (entropy) as eqn. (11),

$$k = \frac{kT}{h} \exp \left(\frac{\Delta S^*}{R} \right) \exp \left(\frac{\Delta E^*}{RT} \right) \quad (11)$$

where ΔS^* and ΔE^* are entropy and internal energy of transition state. In nonionic interactions between iodine and water, ΔS^* and ΔE^* induce some degree of dipole moment in I_2 that cause ΔS^* and ΔE^* changes.

Partition rate of I_2 across a unit cross-sectional area $4/3 \pi r^2$ of solvent with unit concentration gradient (of I_2) without any applied force is correlated as eqn. (12),

$$I_2 \text{ diffusion rate} = 4\pi k D_1 (r_1 + r_2) N_1 \quad (12)$$

I_2 during partition or diffusion encounters the water molecules as eqn. (13),

$$I_2 \text{ encounter} = 4\pi k_1 (r_1 + r_2) N_1 N_2 \quad (13)$$

k_1 is diffusion coefficient of I_2 , r_1 and r_2 are I_2 and H_2O molecular radii and N_1 and N_2 their molecules in encounter. k_2 is diffusion coefficient for monomers from bulk to broken water and numerically it is accountable as eqn. (14),

$$\text{Encounter rate in cage} = 4\pi (k_1 + k_2) (r_1 + r_2) N_1 N_2 \quad (14)$$

$$k_1 = \frac{kT}{6\eta\pi r_1} \text{ or } k_2 = \frac{kT}{6\eta\pi r_2} \quad (15)$$

where k_1 and k_2 are considered as functions of viscosity (η) of solvents. This provokes the application of Stoke's law for I_2 behavior in immiscible solvents as eqn. (15).

Thermodynamically η monitor encounters as eqn. (16),

$$\text{Encounters due to } \eta = \frac{2kT}{3} \eta \left[\frac{(r_1 + r_2)^2}{r_1 r_2} \right] \quad (16)$$

For similar molecules, i.e. I_2-I_2 , $r_1 = r_2$, hence eqn. (16) is reduced to eqn. (17),

$$\text{Encounters for iodon-iodine} = \frac{8kT}{3\eta} \quad (17)$$

Results and Discussion

I₂ concentration obtained by titrating (against a standard Na₂S₂O₃) the samples of organic solvents and water and in presence of urea or thiourea in water phase is plotted in Figs. 1b-14b. I₂ partition coefficient *k* derived by putting its concentrations in eqn. (20) is plotted in Figs. 1-6. Free energies (ΔG^0) plotted in Figs. 1a-7a are obtained from *k* values with eqn. (3) and its regression constants are given in Table 1.

Table 1 Regression constants for partition coefficient vs urea/thiourea conc at 301.15 K

I ₂ in binary and ternary systems	<i>k</i> ⁰	<i>c</i> ²	<i>c</i>	<i>R</i> ²
I ₂ in TDW	85 702	0.6 × 10 ⁻⁴	-2754.3	0.9933
I ₂ in CTC	85 523	441 28	-23 928	0.9924
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CTC	0 530	**	1 390	0.2875
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CTE	96 667	**	-578	0.8844
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CDS	-851.8	-109720	25402	1
I ₂ in (TDW + U) + CDS	393.6	-69760	5840	

Note : *k*⁰ is partition coefficient extrapolated to zero conc. of urea or thiourea in water
 **Linear and *c*² is for polylinear regression fitted to $k = k^0 \pm c$ and $k = k^0 \pm c^0 + c$

Higher I₂ concentration is reported in CTC, and the same decreases in CDS and CTE (Fig. 1b). In water phase with organic solvents, I₂ trend is given in Fig. 2b. But its

concentration in water phase with CTE is seen to manifolds. On urea addition to water phase CTC, I₂ conc. increases in

CTC phase with urea concentration (Fig. 3b) and similar trend is found for water phase too (Fig. 4b). However, I_2 amount transferred to water phase is lower than that of CTC phase (Figs. 4b and 3b). In presence of thiourea, I_2 in CTC (Fig. 5b) and water phases (Fig. 6b) are almost of the same order, but with thiourea concentration, I_2 amount partitioned to water phase is increased (Fig. 6b). Notably, a quantum increase of I_2 concentration is found in CDS phase with urea (Fig. 7b) that matches the I_2 concentration partitioned (eqn. 12) to CTC with water without urea or thiourea (Figs. 1-6). In the counter phase of water I_2 amount is lower and follows increasing trend with urea (Fig. 8b).

With thiourea, I_2 partition to CDS and water follows almost similar trend (Fig. 9b), for water phase, though trend is increasing (Fig. 10b), but I_2 quantity is manifold than that of CDS with urea (Fig. 8b). Comparatively of I_2 amount in CTE with urea, even though it is the same with same trend (Fig. 11b) but its value reduces for water with urea (Fig. 12b), and increases with thiourea (Fig. 14b). It further reduces for CTE with thiourea (Fig. 13b).

These values of I_2 control the trend and quantity of k for its partition, k trend and quantity calculated by eqn. (20) is plotted in Figs. 1-6.

In water and CTC phases, I_2 concentration trend is shown in Figs. 1b and 2b. Remarkably, k value for water with CTC and CDS is higher, and is significantly lower with CTE (Fig. 1) than those of others except (Fig. 4) for (water + thiourea + CTC). Similarly, ΔG^0 values with k (here k is function of urea or thiourea concentration) decrease, incidentally, ΔG^0 values for water + thiourea + CTC, though decrease with k but the values are positive; the positive trend thermodynamically indicates repulsion of I_2 from CTC to water phases as eqns. (8) and (9). Perhaps it may be attributed to the ligand forming capacity of thiourea with water due to the availability of vacant d -orbital on S atom in thiourea than in case of urea where no vacant d -orbital is available. The presence of thiourea molecules in the system induces the polymeric water¹⁴ molecules to be broken up to monomer state as eqns. (10) and (14). In this situation, I_2 molecules tend to preferentially migrate to water phase as eqn. (13). Our experimental data support this line of argument (Figs. 4, 4a, 5b). Among the studied solvents, CTC is the least polar than CDS and CTE, I_2 preferentially going to the CTC phase in comparison to other phases (Fig. 1b).

Urea^{4,11} and thiourea are seen to increase the k values (Figs. 3, 5, 6) prominently except for water + thiourea + CTC (Fig. 4) in comparison to k for pure solvents (water + CTC and CTE + water without urea or thiourea) (Figs. 1b and 1).

The trend of regression constants for k with urea or thiourea given in Table 2 shows the negative k^0 values for

CDS + thiourea (Fig. 5) and at the same time, regression constants for ΔG^0 are negative for all systems (Table 1). K trend : for urea + water + CTC (Fig. 3), urea + water + CDS (Fig. 6), thiourea + water + CTE (Fig. 5) and water + thiourea + CDS (Fig. 6). Though k values for 0.05 mol dm⁻³ of urea or thiourea are reported lower than those of pure water + CTC and water + CDS (Fig. 1b), and at 0.10 mol dm⁻³, k increases but at 0.20 mol dm⁻³ of urea or thiourea k decreases (Figs. 3, 5, 6). The k values with urea for water + CTC (Fig. 3) and with thiourea for water + CTC (Fig. 4) are seen to increase. I_2 partition to water, perhaps may induce transitions as eqns. (10) and (11) leading to increase ΔS of the system and this transition state functions may make urea and thiourea to break down polymeric bulk⁴ water structure^{15,16} producing monomer. Urea + water interactions^{12,17} overcomes van der Waals and dipole-dipole forces⁸ of water, new dipole-induced dipole forces between I_2 and water may establish to hold more and more I_2 . Still I_2 concentration in water is found lower than CTC with lower slope than that the latter. The higher ΔG^0 (Fig. 5a) for I_2 partition in water + CTC shows a greater chemical potential interactions. The highly hydrogen bonded⁷ water structure (bulk) seems to be undisrupted by weaker I_2 interaction, leading to less I_2 concentration to bulk water. This effect could be rationalized to stronger dipole-dipole¹⁸ water interaction and weak dipole induced I_2 interaction. Larger I_2 is detained by less structured CTC with almost zero dipole moment, due to its weak van der Waals forces. Lower k values (Figs. 3, 4) by urea with CDS and thiourea with CTC seem to break down water structure by electrostatic¹⁹ and stronger van der Waals forces due to their lone-pair electron. However, thiourea with CTE initially shows larger k than those of CTC + U and CTE + U, and with concentration, k values decrease (Fig. 3). This trend of k shows greater interaction of TU with water than U with their concentration, marking higher I_2 dissolution in water. As I_2 travels from one to another solvent, Stokes' law as eqn. (16) becomes applicable as function of viscosity of solvents (eqn. 17). TU and U with CDS produces higher k (Figs. 3 and 4) and ΔG^0 (Figs. 6a, 7a) than that of CTE + TU, CTE + U, CTC + U and CTC + TU (Figs. 3, 5, 4, 1a-3a, 2a, 4a, 5a). CDS trend shows that it detains maximum I_2 as it has 2π bonds. Its π -electron may be responsible for such a situation. However, TU and U break down water structure^{2,15,16}, making water less structured. Even though I_2 partition in water with CDS is lower, it means CDS is highly less structured than the broken water structure, and less structured CDS expeditiously collide and encounter with I_2 in cage as eqns. (13) and (14). Contrarily it could be attributed to TU and U making hydrogen bonds with monomer water to higher degree of structuredness²⁰. Comparatively, with TU and U, and their concentration, k values for CDS decreases (Fig. 3) with negative slope (Table 2). This distinguishes higher I_2 partition²¹ to water with their higher ΔS^* , ΔG^* and ΔE^* as eqns. (10) and (11). For TU and U concentration explains reverse effect of I_2

partition to water, this effect could be in the light of physicochemical forces²² acting upon to detain larger I₂. Urea is seen to inhibit I₂ partitioning to CDS, CTC and CTE while its concentration enhances I₂ partitioning in CTE. This trend goes on for CDS and CTE. Value of *K* for CDS with 0.05 and 0.10 mol dm⁻³ of urea increases while gradually decreases with 0.15 mol dm⁻³ (Fig. 3). Thiourea shows similar trend with lower slope (Figs. 3-4) and enhances I₂ partition to water more than urea does. The stronger structure-breaking effect of thiourea on polymeric bulk water produces larger water monomers. These may accommodate large I₂. This effect is rationalized due to its ketonic dipole-dipole structure²² while CTE shows reverse action. Though, urea exhibits similar behavior with mild action.

Table 2. Regression constants for partition coefficients vs free energy at 301.15 K

Systems	G^0	<i>k</i>	R^2
I ₂ in TDW	-8677.1	-28.805	1
I ₂ in U + CTC	-7480.2	-48.247	0.9988
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CTC	3568	-3735.1	0.9909
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CTE	-6218.6	-62.553	0.9742
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CDS	-11317	-8.1538	0.991
I ₂ in (TDW + U) + CDS	-11903	-7.4826	0.9639
I ₂ in (TDW + TU) + CTE	-10068	-15.741	0.9997

Note: ΔG^0 is standard free energy change in Joule extrapolated to zero partition coefficient value obtained by $G = G^0 + k$.

Conclusion : Similar information may be obtained on quaternary oxidation and reduction biomedical solutions with I₂ as a probe molecules that could assist I₂ recover from biological fluids, pharmaceuticals and iodine based disinfectants. Such studies could be very significant for those working with I₂ emulsions, tinctures and radio-medicine. The *k* data may be of some interest for I₂ absorption and adsorption with biopolymer, polymer and disinfectant solutions widely used in hospitals and biological laboratories.

Experimental

I₂ saturated solutions prepared with freshly distilled OS were taken in 250 ml capacity borosil glass bottles. HNO₃ overnight soaked bottles were cleaned with fresh chromic acid and TDW. Substances were weighted to 1 × 10⁻⁵ g accuracy. Test samples (TS) were made to 0.01-ml accuracy in volume (Table 3).

Table 3

System	Addition of solvents and solutions to make TS in ml				
CCl ₄ +I ₂ +(TDW+U)	40+10+50	30+20+50	20+30+50	10+40+50	00+50+50
CS ₂ +I ₂ +(TDW+U)	40+10+50	30+20+50	20+30+50	10+40+50	00+50+50
CTE+I ₂ +(TDW+U)	40+10+50	30+20+50	20+30+50	10+40+50	00+50+50
Total TS in ml	100	100	100	100	100

*Similar system are repeated replacing TDW+U by TDW+TU.

Solutions of 0.05, 0.10 and 0.15 mol dm⁻³ of urea and thiourea were prepared in water. TS with stoppered bottles

were thermostated at 301.15 K (controlled upto 0.001 accuracy with Beckman thermometer) with intermittent shaking avoiding escape of I₂). Temperature control was monitored by auto controlled electric relay. I₂ partition to TDW and OS phases attained equilibrium after a ~45 min. At 30 min interval, an aliquot of each phase with 2-3 drops of freshly prepared starch solution were titrated with standard aqueous thiosulfate solution. Measurements are repeated many times for desired accuracy and precision. Solvents, I₂, urea and thiourea were of A.R. grade (Merck and B.D.H.) and used as received.

Calculation : By titration I₂ normality was calculated as

$$[(N \times V) I_2] = [(N \times V) Na_2S_2O_3]$$

N and *V* are normality and volume of I₂ and Na₂S₂O₃; their concentration is evaluated from equation,

I₂ conc. = Calculated normality of I₂ × its equivalent weight.

I₂ conc. is used for determination of *k*,

$$k = \frac{I_2 \text{ concentration in organic solvent (in g m}^{-3}\text{)}}{I_2 \text{ concentration in water or water + urea or thiourea (in g m}^{-3}\text{)}} \quad (20)$$

References

1. D. M. Mayer and M. J. T. Wounds, *Compend. Clin. Res. Practice*, 1993, **5**, 14; J. Leyden, "Proceedings of the 2nd. International Symposium on Providone", Lexington, 1987.
2. K. Drukker and S. W. de Leeuw, *Chem. Phys. Lett.*, 1998, **291**, 283.
3. L. Costantino, G. D'Errico, P. Roscigno and V. Vitagliano, *J. Phys. Chem. (B)*, 2000, **104**, 7326.
4. A. Nemethy and H. A. Scheraga, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1962, **36**, 3382; L. C. Allen, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1997, **36**, 554.
5. I. Prigogine, "The Molecular Theory of Solutions", Interscience, New York, 1957.
6. L. Buqlang and J. Fu, *J. Chem. Eng. Datu*, 1992, **37**, 2173.
7. J. S. Rawlinson, "Liquids and Liquids Mixtures", Butterworth, London, 1957.
8. T. L. McMalkin in "Techniques of Chemistry", ed. M. R. J. Dack, Wiley-Interscience, New York, 1975, Vol. 8, Part 1.
9. C. Craig and D. Craig, "Extraction and Distribution Technique of Organic Chemistry", Interscience, New York, 1950.
10. S. Cabani, V. Mollica, L. Lepori and S. T. Lobo, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1977, **81**, 982.
11. S. Phang, *J. Aust. Chem.*, 1977, **30**, 1605.
12. T. L. Gottrell, "The Strength of Chemical Bonds", 2nd. ed., Butterworth, London, 1958.
13. G. Borghesani, R. Pednali, F. Pulidori and I. Scaroni, *J. Solution Chem.*, 1989, **18**, 289.
14. F. Frank, "Water, a Comprehensive Treatise", Plenum, New York, 1972, Vol. 1; H. J. V. Tyrrell, "Essays in Structural Chemistry",

- Plenum Press, New York, 1971.
15. F. Shahidi and P. G. Farrell, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1978, 858.
16. K. Drukker, S. W. de Leeuw and S. Hammes-Shiffer, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1998, **108**, 6799.
17. R. Chang, "Intermolecular Forces in Liquids and Solids", McGraw-Hill, New York.
18. S. W. de Leeuw, C. P. Williams and B. Smit, *Mol. Phys.*, 1989, **65**, 1269.
19. S. W. de Leeuw and N. Quirke, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1984, **81**, 880.
20. Y. Yoneda, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1979, **52**, 1297.
21. B. Smit, "Fluid Phase Equilibria : From Atoms to Surfactants", University of Utrecht, 1991.
22. G. C. A. M. Mooij, S. W. de Leeuw, B. Smit and C. P. Williams, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1992, **97**, 5113.